

NEWSLETTER

June 2022 - Sixth Issue

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Dear EEnvest followers,

Now, that our beloved project H2020 EEnvest is rushing towards its final stage and will soon be over and done, it is time to look back at a challenging, inspiring, sometimes stressful but always enjoyable time with our Partners in the project. We reached a lot while cooperating with each other.

EEnvest project aims at creation of frameworks and tools to streamline investment in energy efficiency for buildings, by providing a quantitative evaluation of risks and impact of de-risking measures, and standardized schemes for project quality assessment and technical/financial due diligence.

Technical risks were identified and framed into databases and risk models, then combined with volatility of energy price and uncertainty related to future climate changes into financial risk models. On that solid basis, an innovative methodology was developed to allow investors, in particular impact investors interested in sustainable investments and EU taxonomy alignment, to get reported with standardized financial performance indicators and to benchmark different investment alternatives.

The methodology was validated on EEnvest demonstration sites and further cases from EEnvest database, then implemented as a web service in the blockchain-based EEnvest search & match web platform, to enable user-friendly and secure access to investment opportunities.

EEnvest could connect technical and financial communities, such as building owners, designers, real estate, and private investors.

Do you want to know more? Please find extensive information in [EEnvest booklet](#) and updated [website!](#)

Cristian Pozza,
EEnvest project coordinator (Eurac Research)

EEnvest Final Conference

When
29th June 2022

At what time
9 AM - 1 PM

Online
Google Meet

After 3 years of collaboration, the EEnvest consortium is ready to share the project's final results.

The conference will focus on the EEnvest methodology and results, and the exploitable strategy and future perspectives. There will be the chance also to listen to a roundtable discussion about energy efficiency investments and join the following open debate.

Finally, special guests from QUEST, Triple-A and Launch projects will present their research and results.

Register for free here!

AGENDA

1st part: EEnvest's contribution to energy efficiency investments

- Introduction to EEnvest
- EEnvest methodology and report
- Results of EEnvest
- Conclusions: Exploitation strategy and future perspectives
- Q&A

2nd part: Synergistic projects

- With the participation of the projects **QUEST**, **Triple-A** and **Launch**

3rd part: Expert's roundtable "Future perspectives for de-risking EEI"

- External experts give us their views on the needs and expectations of investments in energy efficiency.
Open debate.

3rd Workshop

“The EEnvest Evaluation Report for Buildings Energy Efficiency Retrofits”

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. The main window displays a presentation slide titled "EEnvest Introduction to the demo-cases Demo-case Olot, Spain". The slide content includes:

- Residential historical building (prior to 1883)
- Rented to local citizens
- Owner: FemNucli, socially responsible investment company
- Complete deep renovation
- Objective of A-Rating in EPC (from G)
- Water reduction, comfort improvement
- EE renovation carried out in 2020-2021

The slide also features a photograph of a multi-story residential building. The Zoom interface shows a gallery view of participants on the right, including Miguel Casas, Stefania Mascolo, Miguel Sastré, Cristian Pozza, Cecile Barrere, Joost Declerck, Tatiana Loureiro, and 12 más. The bottom of the screen shows the Zoom control bar with icons for mute, video, chat, and other functions.

This dissemination workshop took place on 5th May 2022 online and aimed at showing the results of the EEnvest Evaluation Methodology for Energy Efficiency Investments applied to two demo-case buildings in Italy and Spain. The aim of the EEnvest workshop was to present the main EEnvest project results and most particularly the EEnvest investment evaluation report produced by the EEnvest platform based on project input and the de-risking models and multiple-benefits methodology.

Organised by GNE, the workshop number 3 was attended by Energy Efficiency stakeholders with an investor profile. Professionals from retail banks, investment funds and crowdfunding platforms attended

the event and actively participated in the online exchange and event follow-up.

The event started with R2M giving an overview of the main EEnvest project results. Then SINLOC presented the EEnvest Investment Evaluation Report, explaining the different sections of the report, which are the following:

- 1) the project overview,
- 2) the technical risks KPIs,
- 3) the financial performance KPIs,
- 4) the multi-benefit performance KPIs.

The EEnvest report ends with technical, financial and multi-benefit recommendations.

The Italian Demo site / Credits: Prelios Integra

The Spanish Demo site

During the investment case discussion, ENERGINVEST went through the concrete examples of the EEnvest pilot sites in Rome (Italy) and Olot (Spain).

Investor participants made clear that in a society pushing for impact investments and considering the growing EEI market supported by the Renovation Wave and the EU Taxonomy Regulation, the EEnvest report is an attractive and valuable innovative tool proposing EEI de-risking and multi-benefit quantification.

Moreover, investors expressed interest in studying business cases for EEnvest platform and technological bricks exploitation within their organisations. They see plenty of applications to the EEnvest results such as the integration of one or several EEnvest tools in their maturing in-house ESG platform and the development of an EEnvest quality label that could be requested from project promoters looking for bank loans.

The Italian demo site consists of a commercial building managed by Prelios (member of EEnvest's Advisory Board), rented to the International Fund of Agricultural Development (IFAD) in Rome. The building was audited by an external third-party energy auditor during 2017, and a set of renovation actions to cut energy consumption have been carried out. The building's LEED Platinum certification was renewed in 2021.

The Spanish demo case is a residential building located in the city of Olot, Catalonia. The main objective of the project was to submit the whole building to a deep renovation with high energy efficiency measures in order to achieve an A-rating in the Energy Performance Certificate. Besides this, other measures were implemented to reduce the use of other resources, like water, and to improve comfort to families.

4th Workshop

“EEnvest solutions for de-risking investments for renovation in the building sector: stakeholder reactions”

The aim of the workshop was to share the results of the EEnvest project with the actors directly involved in real estate operations development, acting on the post-financing phase of renovation projects, and to other stakeholders interested in real estate investments. At this final stage of the project, as remarked by Eurac Research in the introduction of the workshop, it's very important to involve the building sector and potential project owners to better understand their needs, opinions and remarks in relation to the platform and the EEnvest model.

This fourth workshop started with an overview, by a partner from R2M Solution, of EEnvest project goal, main project results and business cases under evaluation.

In addition, the EEnvest Evaluation Report was explained by a partner from Energinvest with a particular focus on how it can support investments in building energy efficiency projects. After that, a round-table discussion followed with the aim to collect reactions from stakeholders. This more interactive part has seen a fruitful exchange between the speakers and part of the audience, with the emergence of some interesting considerations that helped identify the most relevant KPIs. The multi-benefit performance indicators attracted a lot of attentions, and in particular the CO₂ emissions reductions and social indicators have attracted much interest. Moreover, a short presentation on the Spanish demo case (by Fem Nucli) has proved useful in explaining to the audience how property value can increase after renovation.

The workshop has created interest among the participants, with many questions rising and willingness to see the final form and evolution of the platform. Some of the participants have also made themselves available to follow up with EEnvest partners and further contribute with comments and suggestions in view of the conclusion of the project.

Other dissemination activities 2022

March, 22nd

EEnvest project was presented by Cristian Pozza (project's coordinator) at **QUEST workshop** entitled "Quality Management: De-Risking Green Building Investments to Meet EU Taxonomy Requirements". Cristian's presentation was "Sister Project EEnvest: Risk Reduction for Building Energy Efficiency Investment".

Find more information at [this link](#).

May, 10th

EEnvest project was also presented by Cristian Pozza at **Triple-A Final European Roadshow** "Facilitating Energy Efficiency Project Financing at an Early Stage: Recommendation from the Triple-A project".

You can re-watch the event and find more information by following [this link](#).

CONSORTIUM

Eurac Research
(Italy)

GNE Finance
(Spain)

Sinloc
(Italy)

Energinvest
(Belgium)

IES
(United Kingdom)

R2M Solution
(France)

Politecnico di Milano
(Italy)

UIPI
(Belgium)

Ecrowd!
(Spain)

Register here to the EEnvest Final Conference!

This project has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 833112